

ROLE OF SECURITIES EXCHANGE BOARD OF INDIA IN REGULATING MUTUAL FUNDS

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Abstract:

A mutual fund is a professionally-managed investment scheme, usually run by an asset management company that brings together a group of people and invests their money in stocks, bonds and other securities. In the present paper, an attempt was made to explore the different rules and regulation laid down by SEBI and to analyze the working of SEBI in regulating Mutual Fund Market. The present study has also tried to know the role & effectiveness of SEBI in protection of Investors in Mutual funds. The different scam cases and steps taken by SEBI have been also discussed. It was found that these scams elevated SEBI from a regulatory authority to the level of a statutory authority. It was also found that certain steps have been taken by the SEBI to safeguard the interest of the investors. The present study has concluded that SEBI has taken certain proactive steps to curb these schemes and also given the clear cut instructions for corporate disclosure practices. It has also concluded that the SEBI has imposed a monetary penalty in case of violations of regulations specified and it has also strong emphasised on ex-post investigation and disciplining of mutual funds through financial penalties.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Capital market was growing at a very fast pace in India particularly after liberalization in Industrial Policy in 1991. Controller of Capital Issues (CCI) was looking after new issues. Department of company affairs was also looking after some aspects. However, need was felt to have a single authority to regulate and administer the securities law. With this in mind, SEBI (Securities and Exchange Board of India), which was earlier established as an administrative body in April 1988, was given a statutory status under section 3 of Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992 on 30th January 1992. Controller of Capital Issue (CCI) was abolished with a view to have SEBI as a single agency to look after over capital market.

Mutual Funds: Mutual funds are financial intermediaries which collect the savings of investors and invest them in a large and well diversified portfolio of securities. The major advantages for the investors are reduction in risk, expert professional management, diversified portfolio and tax benefit. By pooling of their assets through Mutual Funds, Investors achieve economies of scale.

Mutual Funds are to be established in the form of Trust under Indian Trust Act, and are to be operated by Asset Management Company (AMC). Mutual Funds dealing exclusively with Money Market Instruments are to be regulated by RBI. Mutual Funds dealing primarily with capital market and also partly in Money Market Instruments are to be regulated by SEBI. All schemes floated by Mutual Funds are to be registered with SEBI.

Working of a mutual fund:

A Mutual Fund is a trust that pools the savings of a number of investors who share a common financial goal. The money thus collected is then invested in capital market instruments such as shares, debentures and other securities. The income earned through these investments and the capital appreciation realized is shared by its unit holders in proportion to the number of units owned by them. Thus a Mutual Fund is the most suitable investment for the common man as it offers an opportunity to invest in a diversified, professionally managed basket of securities at a relatively low cost.

SEBI Regulation on Mutual Funds:

Securities & Exchange Board of India had issued a set of regulations and code of conduct as SEBI (Mutual Fund) Regulations, 1996 on 9th December 1996 for the smooth conduct and regulation of mutual funds. Recently, SEBI has issued updated regulations as SEBI (Mutual fund) Regulations 2011 on 07 Jan 2012 covering all amendments up to Dec 2011. These guidelines lay down certain criteria for investment, disclosure, accountability and distribution of profits to its members. The salient features of these regulations include various aspects relating to Registration of Mutual Fund, Constitution and management of mutual fund & rights and obligations of trustees, Constitution and management of Asset Management Company and custodian, Restrictions on business activities of AMC and its obligations, Schemes of mutual fund, Investment objectives and valuation policies, Advertisement code, Code of conduct, Restrictions on investments, Investment valuation norms, Accounts and Offer documents.

3 Significance of the present Study: Today there are around 60 mutual funds and over 450 schemes with total assets of around Rs.8.84 lacs crores. This fast grown industry is regulated by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI). Today the investor is being offered service standard (daily NAV, reduced transaction time, on the query answering etc.) comparable to that of western countries. And has a choice of a diverse range of products, with Internet being widely used, mutual funds minimize the costs and improve turnaround time in transactions in future. Since the mutual funds involve a huge amount of investors, therefore, it has been tried and analyzed whether SEBI regulatory role is up to the mark or have some shortcomings.

Objectives of The Present Study: The present study tried to explore the different rules and regulation laid down by SEBI and to analyze the working of SEBI in regulating Mutual Fund

Market. The present study has also tried to know the role & effectiveness of SEBI in protection of Investors in Mutual funds. The different scam cases and steps taken by SEBI have been also discussed.

Scope of the Present Study

The scope of study is limited to exploratory study of role of SEBI in regulating mutual funds in India to find out the problem face by investors in investing mutual fund and the steps taken by the SEBI to protect the interest of investors and how far SEBI was successful to protect the interest of investors.

DEVELOPMENT OF SEBI THROUGH THE 3 DECADES

1. Harshad Mehta Securities Fraud (1988-1995) In 1988, SEBI had limited powers. Chiefly it regulated the securities market and ensured its constant development. SEBI had no control over the transactions taking place between the brokers and the investors. However, the scenario changed completely after the Harshad Mehta Securities fraud. Harshad Mehta was a stockbroker and started his own securities firm in 1990 and misused his status to manipulate the stock prices of certain shares on the scrip for his personal financial gain.

Basically what Harshad Mehta has invested large sums of money in particular share. Seeing him invest, the other shareholders and investors also invested in the same shares. This resulted in unnatural pumping of money into the stock markets causing a rise in the price of these shares on the scrip. Unnatural inflation of stock prices resulted in the Bull Run. This Bull Run increased the share price of companies like Associated Cement Company (ACC), the first company Mehta invested in the stock markets, from Rs.200/- to Rs.9000/- a 4400% increase over the course of one year (1991-1992).

The above operation though immoral was not illegal but the problem arose because Mehta obtained capital to invest in the stock markets by misappropriating banks' money. When banks gave Mehta cash to purchase government securities owned by other banks, he invested this money into the stock markets, sold the purchased shares at a profit after a period of 7 days or so and then completed the purchase of government securities. The money handed over to Mehta was given for a specific purpose and he wrongfully used the money for personal gain. This falls

within the scope of money laundering. Thus, Mehta made approximately Rs. 5000 crores by investing misappropriated money in the securities markets.

Mehta owned 50 lakh shares of more than 130 companies. When his scam was revealed by Sucheta Dalal, a renowned journalist of the time, he offloaded most of his shares to save himself from prosecution. Investors felt that they had been cheated by Mehta and sold of their share holdings. The Bull Run Phenomenon is defined as the large scale purchase of securities resulting in the increase in price on the scrip in order to safeguard them themselves. This unabated selling caused the markets to lose Rs. 0.1million⁴¹² in 1 day.

SEBI, having no authority to regulate the transactions between investors and brokers, and wash and icapped. The only authority with the jurisdiction to look into the matter was the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI).The government was made aware of this major gap in the regulation of securities markets and after introspection they decided to bestow SEBI with greater powers promoting it to the status of “market regulators”. In lieu of this, the Legislature speedily approved the SEBI Act, 1992.

The SEBI Act gave SEBI a 3 fold duty-

1. Protection function- To protect the stock markets from unscrupulous investors and to protect the investors from unfair market practices.
2. Development Function- To develop the stock markets healthily and lawfully.
3. Regulation Function-: To regulate the transactions between brokers, investors and the stock market to ensure fair play.

In addition to this, the SEBI Act, 1992 deemed SEBI a statutory authority with a separate legal existence.The 1992 scam elevated SEBI from a regulatory authority to the level of a statutory authority.

2. Harshad Mehta Securities Scam (1996-2000)

This development of SEBI between 1988- 1995 was evident when Mehta tried to pull off a 2ndscam in 1997.

In 1997, Mehta tried to re-enter the markets by creating a network of front companies calledout of the Dayamnti Group. This group operated same office as Mehta’s 1990 securities firm.Mehta

employed brokers and agents who bought and sold shares at the stock market on his behalf for a commission. Harshad Mehta even managed to find companies (e.g. - BPL, Videocon and Sterlite Industries) who gave him start-up capital to set up this second venture in exchange for him inflate the price of their shares in the stock market.

Mehta stuck to his original modus operandi of investing large sums of money into certain shares and tried to bring about a Bull Run. However the investors and SEBI had become too smart to fall for Harshad Mehta’s tricks.

In 1998, SEBI having smelled foul play in the sudden increase of certain share prices on the scrip investigated the matter, managed to link the Damayanti Group to Harshad Mehta and his associates through telephone bills, payment to lawyers, investment details, etc. and filed a case against Harshad Mehta and his associates in the courts. SEBI curbed Harshad Mehta before he could harm the investors and manipulate the markets. In 10 years, SEBI had already grown immensely and was well on its way to becoming the market watchdog.

List of Changes by SEBI after the Harshad Mehta Securities Scam

1. Strict full disclosure norms were introduced. The full disclosure norms were with Respect to material facts, specific risk factors, prudential norms, etc.
2. The Listing Agreement was introduced and adherence to it was made mandatory by all listed companies.
3. A code of advertisement was introduced to ensure that companies disclosed all the information in an honest and trusted manner to the investors at the time of making a public offer for purchase of securities.
4. The National Stock Exchange (NSE) with online, screen based, nation-wide electronic trading was introduced to increase transparency of operations.
5. The Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) switched over to online, screen based trading.
6. A revised “carry forward” system replaced the “badla” system.
7. Guidelines regarding requirements of full disclosure to SEBI were introduced.
8. Requirements to be fulfilled before making public offers for purchase of securities to the public were also introduced.

3. Satyam Scandal (2001-2008) The Satyam Scandal came to light on 7th January, 2009 by way of a confession letter written by B. Ramalinga Raju (the Founder and Chairman of Satyam Computers Services Limited) published in the Times of India. In the confession letter Raju confessed to manipulating his books of accounts by overstating assets by Rs. 2161 crores understating liabilities by Rs. 1020 crores, including nonexistent interest worth Rs. 376 crores and inflating cash reserves by Rs. 5040 crores.

In addition to this Ramalinga Raju obtained loans worth Rs. 2000 crores from nonbanking financial companies (NBFC's) by offloading shares worth thousands of crores illegally into front companies to portray a better financial condition than the reality. There were charges of money Laundering levied on Raju because he used the illegally obtained money from NBFC's for the purpose of purchasing land.

The whole scam cost the markets approximately Rs. 14,000 crores. The books of accounts are a reflection of the company's financial standing. They are important tools that enable investors and shareholders to determine whether or not they want to invest in a particular company. Ramalinga Raju manipulated the books of accounts to cheat investors and shareholders into believing that the company was doing better than the reality. Raju managed to run the scam past the auditors, Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC) for 7 years. Raju flouted SEBI Regulations of Fraudulent and Unfair Trade Practices (FUTP), SEBI Regulations for Prevention of Insider Trading (PIT) and SEBI Regulations for Issue of Capital and Full Disclosure Requirements (ICDR). The Satyam Scam was a major setback to SEBI. However, SEBI managed to hit back strongly. It investigated the matter and readjusted the books of accounts to reflect the real financial position of the company. After a complete study into the scam, SEBI released an order which was the first of its kind. SEBI held Ramalinga Raju and the 9 major associates including B. Rama Raju (the Managing Director), Vadlamai Srinivas (Chief Financial Officer), G. Ramakrishna (Vice President) and V.S. Prabhakara Gupta (Head of Internal Audit) guilty of insider trading, indulging in fraudulent and unfair trade practices and violation of Clause 41 of the listing agreement 415-416. In its order SEBI ordered the 10 accused to pay Rs. 1850 crores + 12% simple interest (roughly amounting to Rs. 3000 crores) within 45 days and banned any of them

from accessing the securities markets in any way for 14 years This order, along with the changes introduced by SEBI, was a message to the securities markets and the investor communities that SEBI was becoming stronger. The order spoke volumes of the growth SEBI has seen in 20 years of its existence. Even though SEBI was not successful in detecting the scam on its own, it managed to lash back strongly to ensure such a scam never occurred again.

List of Changes by SEBI after the Satyam Scandal-:

1. A record of all transactions with respect to the stock markets to be maintained by the companies for inspection by SEBI
2. Regular monitoring of all transactions by SEBI between investors, shareholders, brokers and the company.
3. Special attention to large, unusual transactions by SEBI while inspection of balance sheets.
4. Appointment of the Chief Financial Officer (CFO) to be made by the Audit Committee after proper assessment of their background, qualifications, etc.
5. Appointment of Independent Directors on the Board to ensure the fair and honest functioning of the company. No stock options to be given to these directors and the salary should also be given in the form of reimbursements.
6. Several audit norms were introduced like the mandatory rotation of auditors/ audit firms every 5 years.
7. Preventing auditors from undertaking any non-audit related to activities to ensure that the auditors are true to their work and there is no conflict of interest.
8. Adoption of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by all major Companies in the preparation of various financial reports by the companies.
9. Interim Disclosure of balance sheet figures (audited balances of major account heads) on a half yearly basis.
10. Strict timelines for the submission of various financial reports to SEBI throughout the Year.

4. Sahara Scam (2009- Present)

The Sahara Scam is the biggest victory for SEBI in recent times. Sahara India floated 2 new companies- Sahara India Real Estate Corporation Limited (SIRECL) and Sahara Housing

Investment Corporation (SHIC) in 2005 by registering them under the Companies Act, 1956 with the relevant Registrar of Companies in Kanpur and Maharashtra. In the annual meetings held by both the companies, a resolution was passed to raise funds through private placement of optionally fully convertible debentures (OFCD's) from the friends, associates, and family members of the Board of Directors.

Funds were also to be raised through the circulation of an information memorandum to a few trusted investors. The date of commencement of issues of the debentures was 25th April, 2008 and 20th November, 2009, respectively. SIRECL collected Rs. 17,656.53 crores (net value) between 25th April, 2008 and 13th April, 2011. SHICL collected Rs. 6373.20 crores (net value) between 20th November, 2009 and 13th April, 2011. Thus both the companies collected Rs. 24,029.73 crores from 30 million investors over a period of 3 years.

In 2009, when a red herring prospectus for Sahara Prime City (a real estate venture of Sahara India) was submitted to SEBI for approval, SEBI noticed unusual fund raising activity in the 2 firms-SHICL and SIRECL.

On 4th January, 2010, SEBI received a complaint from a man, Roshan Lal, who alleged that "illegal means were being used by SHICL and SIRECL in issuance of OFCD's."

Private Placement of Shares is defined as issue of invitation for purchase of shares sent individually to each investor and not an open invitation to public for purchase of securities. Private Placement of securities generally happens when individual invitation to purchase securities is sent to 50 or less people.

Following this, SEBI launched an investigation against Sahara India, inquiring into the fund raising activities of SHICL and SIRECL along with investor information. On following through with the investigation and finding Sahara guilty, SEBI passed an interim order, ordering the payment of Rs. 24,000 crores + 17% interest to 30 million investors. The SEBI order was passed by the Securities Appellate Tribunal (SAT) and subsequently the Supreme Court on 12th August, 2012. This was the first time in the history of SEBI that it had caught such a huge scam on its own. SEBI's vigilance and alertness, the expansion of its powers and its strong investigative instinct was revealed in this scam. Detecting the Sahara Scam is a massive achievement for SEBI and is a testament to the growth of SEBI in the last 3 decades since its inception in 1988.

However, the Sahara Scam is also the biggest securities scam in India. It resulted in 30 million investors losing their hard earned money. The fact that it was detected after 3 years and had cost the markets Rs. 25,000 crores was a matter for concern. Thus the government has taken steps to tighten SEBI's hold on the securities markets still further and has bestowed more powers on the SEBI.

List of Changes made in SEBI after the Sahara Scam:-

1. Before the Sahara Scam, the term “private placement” had not been defined in the Companies Act. Only those instances where an offer would not qualify as a “public offer” had been defined. On SEBI's recommendation, was introduced in the Companies (Amendment) Act, 2013. It defined private placement “as any issue of securities by a listed or an unlisted public company to 49 or less people where individual invitations to buy are sent to the investors.” As soon as the number of investors rose to 50 and beyond, the issue of shares would be declared a public offer and would have to be verified and approved by the SEBI.
2. The government gave SEBI the power to regulate any money pooling worth Rs.100 crores or more.
3. The government has given SEBI the authority to seize the assets of the people who do not comply with the “seize and search” orders issued by the SEBI Chairman.
4. The government has instructed SEBI to create a new law to control illicit investment schemes. SEBI is in the process of drafting this law and sending it to the required authorities for approval.
5. SEBI now has the right to retrieve and investigate the telephone records, etc. with respect to any securities investigation.
6. Chit funds, nidhi schemes and housing schemes (investment schemes) that are not regulated by any particular authority and have a corpus greater than Rs.100 crores have to be regulated by SEBI and follow all regulations as deemed fit by SEBI.

STEPS TAKEN BY THE SEBI TO SAFEGUARD THE INTEREST OF MUTUAL FUNDS

6.1 Securities Market Awareness Campaign

SEBI believes that 'An Educated Investor is a Protected Investor.' A comprehensive Securities Market Awareness Campaign was launched on January 17, 2003. The campaign includes workshops, audio-visual clippings, distribution of educative materials in English, Hindi and local languages, a dedicated investor website with inventory of booklets/pamphlets/FAQ's and periodic advertisements in All India Radio (AIR) and print media. Till Mar'12, 3217 workshops were conducted covering around 493 cities/towns in India.

6.2 Recognition to Investor Associations: SEBI recognizes investor associations, extends financial support for conducting investor education programmes, and also addresses various issues raised by them to protect the interest of the investors. SEBI has so far recognized 10 Investors' Associations.

6.3 Portfolio Disclosure: Transparency is essential for corporate governance and portfolio disclosure is an important means of keeping the investors informed about the way their moneys are being used to create financial assets. Therefore, SEBI has made it mandatory for mutual funds to disclose the entire portfolio of any scheme.

6.4 Transparency in Investment Decisions

SEBI has taken a far-reaching step towards ensuring due diligence and transparency in all investment decisions by advising all mutual funds 'to maintain records in support of each investment decision which will indicate the date, facts and opinion leading to that decision'.

6.5 Screening of mutual funds at the entry level:

Every mutual fund shall be registered with SEBI and the registration is granted on the fulfillment of certain conditions laid down in the regulations for 'efficient and orderly conduct of the affairs of a mutual fund'.

6.6 SEBI has outlined the advertisement code too:

All mutual funds are bound to publish a scheme-wise annual report or an abridged summary through an advertisement within six months of the closure of the financial year. The trustees of a mutual fund are bound to convey to the investors any information that has an adverse impact. A mutual fund is also to publish half-yearly unaudited financial results through an advertisement.

6.7 Prescribed Norms for Investment

SEBI has prescribed norms for investment management with a view to minimizing/reducing undue investment risks. There are also certain restrictions, which are aimed at ensuring transparency and prohibiting mutual funds from excessive risk exposure. These restrictions and limitations have strong similarities with those imposed in the US and the UK.

6.8 Inspection & Penalties

SEBI inspects the books of accounts, records and documents of a mutual fund, the trustees, AMC and custodian. SEBI also imposes a monetary penalty in case of violations of regulations specified. The regulatory framework indicates that SEBI is a highly powerful regulator. There is strong emphasis on ex-post investigation and disciplining of mutual funds through financial penalties.

PROBLEMATIC ASPECTS FOR FURTHER REGULATION

An analytical view of crucial issues for further regulations is presented here.

7.1 Voting Right to Mutual Funds:

As per Companies Act, trust cannot exercise any voting power, but it can be exercised by a public trustee who is a government official, which is as good as not exercising at all. The recently formed AMFI has urged for voting rights to mutual funds so as to have a say in decision-making. Mutual Funds sponsors like bank and Financial Institutions, in their role as merchant bankers and lenders have access to inside information which coupled with voting rights encourage the fund managers to indulge in unscrupulous practices, such as insider trading where regulations are weak. Undoubtedly, firm's wealth would improve, but it may be at the cost of the corporate health.

7.2 Ceiling on Corpus Amount:

SEBI regulations have not stipulated any maximum amount to be collected under each scheme. Retention of oversubscribed amount creates difficulty not only in management of the fund but eventual problems may crop up at the time of redemption also. Therefore, there should be a limit on the retention of oversubscribed amount. The other viewpoint is, if limitation on corpus amount is imposed, the entry for more and more investors into the mutual fund would be closed and the objective of mutual funds gets defeated. However, in the present situation where the mutual fund industry is in the nascent stage and not fully professionalized.

7.3 Capital Adequacy:

Safety of the principal amount can be achieved by guarantee offered by the Government, like post-office saving deposits. Alternatively, safety can be assured through capital adequacy, which is presently applicable to bank deposits, debentures and equity shares. Mutual Funds, whose main activity is to invest in marketable securities, are put to risk of default. The collapse of market may affect the interest of investors and safety of depositors, the investor, and the AMCs should have capital adequacy norms. The norms are to be formulated after a thorough study of the issue.

7.4 Borrowing powers:

SEBI regulations have not specified about borrowing powers. The basic feature of open-ended Mutual Funds is to provide liquidity by continuous repurchase and resale. On repurchase requisition, the fund will sell some of its securities and meet the investor requirement. But if the fund invests in securities-which are not liquid able at optimum/fair price or the encashment may be delayed because of various reasons. In this context, SEBI regulations may have to permit open-ended fund to borrow in order to accommodate the liquidity interest of the investor.

7.5 Insurance coverage for Mutual Fund Investors:

Deposit Insurance Corporation of India provides an insurance coverage to some extent to deposit holders of banks. Similarly, Mutual Fund investors should also have such coverage against the risks associated. In the UK, Securities and Investments Board organizes a compensation fund-which is contributed by financial services companies including unit trusts.

7.6 Norms for Portfolio Turnover Rate:

Portfolio turnover rate indicates the extent of portfolio activity and depends on the investment objective of the scheme. The turnover rate also influences the stock market price level, investment costs and the level of risk associated. SEBI regulations do not specify norms for portfolio turnover rate for different schemes. Portfolio turnover rate should to be disclosed in the annual report.

7.7 Nomination Facility:

To facilitate easy transmission of the units, mutual funds should be permitted to provide the service of nomination facility to the unit holders. Presently UTI is offering such facility to its unit holders. The same should be extended to other mutual funds by amending the SEBI regulations.

7.8 Shared Trustees:

The trustee has the power of superintendence and direction over AMCs. They monitor the performance and compliance of SEBI regulation. Many trustees are associates with more than one mutual fund that may diversify the attention of a trustee and cannot fully entertain the interest of a particular mutual fund.

OVER REGULATION – IS THAT THE NEW PROBLEM?

In the above paper we have seen the growth of SEBI in the last 3 decades. Since its inception, SEBI has been constantly subject to change. Every few months there are amendments to the powers and duties of SEBI. The list of key aims and objectives of SEBI are also constantly changed by master circulars, orders, etc. From practically no powers when it was formed in 1988, SEBI has become the prime market regulator for the stock exchanges in India. SEBI has the power to react to problems, investigate situations, protect the investors, brokers, banks, companies, etc. and develop the securities markets. SEBI also needs to be proactive and institute policies in anticipation of situations contingent in nature. For instance after the Satyam Scam, SEBI has instituted policies to verify the balance sheets of companies listed on the NSE and BSE on a quarterly basis, to bring about mandatory rotation of auditors/audit firms dealing with a company and enforcing a whistleblower policy in each company. These reforms were necessary and relevant. However, SEBI has been going overboard in its regulation off late.

In recent times, every time there has been a scam or a problem related to the securities markets, the government has dumped SEBI with greater powers and responsibilities. Some of the powers are redundant and restrict fair business practices. Due to certain large scale scams in the recent past, SEBI has become over vigilant and is conducting investigations that are unnecessary and time consuming.

A classic example of this over vigilance is the recent induction of S.42 in the Companies (Amendment) Act, 2013 that defines private placement as *“any offer or invitation to not more than 49 people by way of a personal invitation for purchase of securities.”* As soon as the number rises to beyond 50, SEBI will step in and demand for verification prior to the issue of invitation for purchase of securities. This section was added as a reaction to the Sahara Scam where Subrata Roy duped 30 million investors of Rs. 25, 000 crores by private placement of optionally fully convertible debentures (OFCD's).

Since then, SEBI has initiated hundreds of investigations against medium and large companies to enquire into the method of issue of securities to shareholders. Most of these investigations are a waste of time. SEBI is trying to overcompensate for the lack of foresight in the Sahara Case by putting every third company under the scanner. Even if a small company wants to raise money from its family members, SEBI will initiate elaborate verification processes before giving its approval.

Another example of over regulation by SEBI was the DLF Case. In this case, SEBI passed an order banning the company from dealing in the securities markets for 3 years because of the company's failure to mention certain material facts during the SEBI approval process before getting listed on the stock exchange. When this order was appealed in the SAT, it was quashed immediately. SAT accused SEBI of over regulation and justified its decision on the grounds that penalizing every company by banning their entry into the stock markets would cause the markets to collapse.

SEBI is supposed to understand the root cause of the problem and rectify it. Uprooting the company from the securities markets will result in huge losses to the investors and shareholders and prove useless.

In my opinion, SEBI is being overburdened with too many functions. It would be more conducive if SEBI had a varied but relevant bouquet of responsibilities that would ensure efficient functioning of the regulatory authority. The overregulation happening currently must stop. It is tiresome and needs to be done away with so that SEBI does not drown in its pool of duties and maintains its position as the market watchdogs.

Guidelines of SEBI

The AMCs are bound to disclose all the relevant data that is necessary for the investment purpose of investors.

Following measures can be taken by the company for getting higher investments in the mutual fund schemes:

- Educate the agents or the salesmen properly so that they can take up the queries of the customer effectively.
- Set up separate customer care divisions where the customers can anytime pose their query, regarding the scheme or the current NAV etc. These customer care units can work out in accordance with the requirements of the customer and facilitate them to choose the scheme that suits their financial status.
- Conduct seminars or programs about mutual fund where every information about the product is outlined including the risk factor associated with the different classes of assets.
- Brokers should reduce the brokerage charges for intraday and delivery based so that the investor can save more amounts to generate extra investment for the investor as well as for the Mutual Fund companies.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY: Emerging markets like India promise to increasingly embrace growth as they gain the confidence of the investor, as against the dip in investor's confidence in advanced countries like US, UK and Japan. Against this backdrop, mutual funds have emerged as a suitable investment option with their characteristic transparency, flexibility and low cost of investment. SEBI being a premiere institution for dealing with the problems

relating to securities has advanced a long way towards protecting the investors from the hazards of the predators existing in the market. On the positive front, many banks sponsored mutual fund had launched assured return schemes and lured the investor's huge contribution. However at the time of maturity could not match the assured return. Sponsored bank also tried to raise their hands eg. Canara Bank, Indian, State Bank of India etc. SEBI gave directive to sponsor bank to honour the commitment made by the mutual funds. Shortfall of more than Rs 2000 crores was met by sponsor banks for benefit of small investors.

By beginning of the new millennium in 2000, SEBI has strengthened and established itself as an all-powerful regulatory body for the capital market, all intermediaries in it, SROs, stock Exchanges, listed companies, Venture Funds, Mutual Funds etc. These measures include permission for e-broking, share trading via net with orders to be routed through the websites of brokers, acceptance of Kumar mangalan Birla Report on Corporate Governance and of K.B. Chande shekhar Panel Report on Venture Funds. The SEBI has given directives to the listed companies and to the top 150 companies in particular to observe the code of corporate governance by March end 2001. The contrary scenario was that only the big fishes could escape the net and the small ones were still striving to uphold their existence. The present study has concluded that SEBI has taken certain proactive steps to curb these schemes and also given the clear cut instructions for corporate disclosure practices. It has also concluded that the SEBI has imposed a monetary penalty in case of violations of regulations specified and it has also strong emphasised on ex-post investigation and disciplining of mutual funds through financial penalties.

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